

SOCIAL NETWORKS OR INTERNATIONAL INTERNET SYSTEMS

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Abstract: The article reflects information about the increasing penetration of social networks into our lives, changes, events and news taking place in our country and the world.

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In the rapidly developing information age, there is no way not to use the Internet and social networks or not to turn to them. Because, especially social networks are the main tool in the formation of a person's worldview, in the further expansion of his spiritual world. This is a happy situation on the one hand. Today, we, young people, use these great opportunities as much as we want, and use our time more productively during study or work. If we look at it from today's point of view, the Internet, which has already become a global network, has become the most important area among mass media with its speed and borderlessness, and has even created an opportunity to quickly and easily find answers to complex questions that we are thinking about.

If we look at the emergence of the Internet, it begins with the RAND CORPORATION, one of the first research centers of the United States, when it was first proposed to create a decentralized computer network that would cover the entire country. The purpose of the implementation of this project was to centralize the management of military institutions, scientific and educational centers by uniting computers into one network. The goal was to create a system that would remain operational even in the face of a nuclear weapon attack, even if multiple parts of the network were down. Such a system can be implemented only when there is a large number of networks. Thus the Internet was founded. Later, the ARPANET network was created, consisting of 4 networks located in the most prestigious testing institutes of the USA. Originally intended for use by scientists in research work, the network later became a computerized chain of selling nonsense. Nevertheless, it was one of the most successful inventions of the 20th century. At the end of this century, it was called ARPANET-INTERNET and was recognized as a system consisting of a collection of very powerful computers and networks.

At the moment, many great people who are benefiting the people of the world are conducting many researches in order to improve the quality of the Internet. Among them, one of the most successful people in the world, the owner of many large companies, Elon Musk, aimed to put the Starlink satellite into orbit to implement the Starlink project in order to provide the world with a high-quality Internet network, and until now managed to launch 420 satellites. This is 20% of all satellites in the sky. As of March 31, 2019, the total number of satellites in orbit has reached 2062.

The world continues to change day by day. The advent of social media has changed the way we live and communicate, for better and for worse. Its effect is that we all cannot imagine the world without social networks such as WhatsApp, Instagram, Facebook, Twitter or TikTok. Undoubtedly, this globalization and the dominance of the Internet in society has created something bad or morally questionable. On the other hand, it has also made our lives easier, ushered in a new era of entertainment, and allowed us to come out of hiatus. Communication frontiers have made it possible for everyone in this world to connect with each other. As we know, the social networks used by the world's population are definitely a pillar of this process. Most of us are not aware that some popular social networks earn an average of \$7.89 per user. On average, 55.1% of the population of the world are active users of social networks. But which social networks are used the most?

Facebook, recognized as the king of social networks, occupies the first place in the list of the most used social networks by the population of the world with 2.74 billion active users. This network connecting the whole world was founded by Mark Zuckerberg in 2004. Facebook is one of the most valuable companies in the world and one of the top five technology companies in the world, along with Microsoft, Google, Apple and Amazon. Social networking based on sharing content and connecting with your network of friends is one of the biggest businesses in the world. And in recent years, no network can take its place.

YouTube (2.291 billion) is a social network founded in 2005 and based on video sharing (although it is the second largest in the world after Facebook). It was acquired by Google in October 2006 for \$1.65 billion. Every minute, more than 500 hours of videos are uploaded to the platform, and its ad monetization generates approximately \$15,000 million in annual revenue for YouTube.

WhatsApp (2 billion) is the world's main instant messaging social network, one of only three networks to reach 2,000 million monthly active users. It was launched in February 2009 and is the main messaging app in most of the world (except the Chinese market). In February 2012, he bought it from Facebook for \$21.8 billion.

Facebook Messenger (1.3 billion) is an instant messaging application owned by Facebook. It was part of Facebook's private social network, although the messaging app itself was launched in August 2012. Currently, its main competitor is Zoom, which has been the most popular in recent years. is an advanced messaging service.

Instagram (1.221 million). We have reached the position of the top five. Social network Instagram with 1221 million monthly active users is in fifth place on the list. This network was launched in October 2010 and is currently an American app owned by Facebook. Also, Telegram, Snapchat and TikTok, which are the most used in Uzbekistan, are also included in this list, TikTok is in eighth place with its 689 million subscribers, and Telegram and Snapchat are in tenth place in a row. it occupies the second and thirteenth places with about 500 million subscribers.

The British "Cable" portal found answers to questions about internet speed that have been of interest to all internet users until now. It contains data collected by "Cable" experts for 200 countries over 12 months. In this, it was calculated how much time it takes to download a video with HD quality and 5GB size at the average speed of the internet available in the country. Singapore took the first place in the list. Internet speed in this country was 60 mb/s. A 5GB file took 11 minutes to download in Singapore. Sweden and Denmark took second and third place in the rating. Internet speed in these countries is 46 and 43 Mb/s, respectively. Uzbekistan is on the 184th place in the rating. It states that the average internet speed in our country is 1.02 Mb/s. As an example, it is shown that it takes more than 11 hours to download a video in HD quality and 5GB in size in Uzbekistan. For comparison, Russia occupies the 47th place in the rating (13 Mb/s). Kazakhstan is on 95th place (4.4 Mb/s), Kyrgyzstan is on 163rd place (1.52 Mb/s). Only Tajikistan (188th place, 0.94 Mb/s) and Turkmenistan (198th place, 0.56 Mb/s) are lower than Uzbekistan.

In conclusion, the internet is one of the best inventions ever made by mankind. The amount of things you can do on the internet is huge.. It's an absolutely amazing tool to learn different things and communicate with people anywhere in the world with just one click of the mouse. However, its unlimited accessibility and its influence on the minds of the young people who access it cause us concern. The Internet shows a wide range of illogical videos or images that can cause various psychological effects on this young generation, while excessive use of the computer can cause physical problems and negative effects on the mind of users. The Internet can be really useful and interesting, but for those who do not know how to use it, it has many dangers and dark sides.

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